

*Ben Neill and LEMUR*

Ben Neill and Eric Singer

Ben Neill will present a set with the LEMUR robots and his newly redesigned mutantrumpet, a hybrid electro-acoustic instrument. In this new set of future dub jazz, the LEMUR robots provide dubstep rhythms live in real time and are combined with deep sub basslines and the otherworldly sonic explorations of the mutantrumpet. Neill's instrument allows him to interact with the robots in a variety of ways, bringing an improvisatory element to the show.